

The Effect Of The Curriculum Of Exercises To Correct The Errors Of The Initial Learning Processes In Developing The Technical And Planning Performance Of The Stadium Defense Skill For Players Of Specialized Volleyball Schools

Wathiq Abdulsahib Oubed, Raja Abdulsamad Ashoor, Shehab Ghalib Shehab

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 06, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 06, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Volleyball Schools, Technical And Planning, Researchers, Motor Program</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4904702</p>	<p><i>At the forefront of the research, the researchers demonstrated the importance of building the motor program in a scientifically correct construction free of errors, as it is by repetition and practice is rooted and proven and becomes an original part of the motor program, which affects the skill performance and thus the team's planning performance. The player sometimes distorts the program forever. The researchers worked on building exercises that combined the development of the skillful performance to defend the stadium and the planning requirements for that skill by making carefully studied changes to the wrong motor program, trimming and modifying it, and developing the skill and planning aspect at the same time. The players of the Specialized Volleyball School in Basra Governorate - Abi Al-Khasib for the year 2019-2020 and the sample consisted of 14 players, who made up 77% of the original research community. My skills are up to date to test players.</i></p>

Introduction

Learning processes in sports are considered one of the most important stages of building movements and skills for different sports, where the movement program for these skills is built and established for the next stages of development of the movements of the athlete as well as the movement program. Linking it to other movements is easier to form a kinematic sentence or be part of the formation of my team's plans to score a point or win. The plan will not be successful unless all of its vehicles are at a good level of mastery.

Among those activities is the volleyball game that has undergone many studies and research, using various means and sciences in order to establish an educational base based on solid scientific foundations for its practitioners, trying to keep learning processes away from errors, as volleyball does not allow mistakes because the error costs a point loss because of its speed of performance. And determine the touches of the ball. Among these skills is the defense skill of the stadium, which is characterized by a high speed of performance, its difficult technical requirements and the speed of reaction. Therefore, the game of volleyball requires a distinguished number of learners, observing and analyzing movements, and working to modify learning paths by multiple means skill and planning performance during the debugging process for initial learning.

Research problem

The game of volleyball is one of the games that received a good share of attention from practitioners and observers and ranked high among other events in many countries in the world, and in Iraq it gained wide popularity and through the researchers' follow-up, they found that the skills of this game took a loss of aesthetics, as well as a failure. Achieving skills for their goals during matches is due to the lack of scientific knowledge of many educational programs and the weakness of those in charge of them from discovering the errors of initial learning and knowing their causes and setting the correct entries, and from here came the question: Can the technical and planning performance of the players of specialized schools in volleyball be developed without the use of corrective skill-based exercises?

Research objective

Identify the effectiveness of exercises to correct the initial learning errors proposed in developing the skill of defending the stadium for players of specialized volleyball schools.

Research hypotheses

- 1- There are differences of statistical significance between the results of the pre and post tests for the skill of defending the stadium for the players of specialized volleyball schools.
- 2- There are differences of statistical significance between the results of the dimensional tests and in favor of the experimental group.

Research areas

- 1- The human field: Players of specialized volleyball schools in Basra Governorate for the year 2019/2020
- 2- Time domain: for the period from 1/10/2019 to 1/10/2020
- 3- Spatial domain: the hall of the specialized school volleyball in Abi Al-Khasib/ Basra Governorate

Definition of Terms:

Learning errors: They are errors associated with the learning processes that arise during the construction of the motor program of effectiveness as a result of incorrect learning that increases steadily with repetition operations if not modified by those in charge of the learning process that negatively affects the individual and planning performance of the team in later stages.

Research methodology and field procedures**Research Methodology**

The researchers used the experimental method with one of the experimental designs with equal groups of pre and post measurement due to its suitability to the nature of the problem to be solved, as it is "one of the most sufficient means in reaching the knowledge of the problem, as it is through it that the event can be predicted and controlled by studying the causes and their interpretation (6: 168).

The research sample

The research sample was intentionally chosen from the players of the Specialized School of Volleyball for the 2019/2020 season, as it consisted of (18) players, four players were excluded for not participating in the tests, as the sample was divided into two equal groups (7) players for each group, a control group and an experimental group. The percentage of the sample was (77%) from the original community, and the researchers conducted homogeneity and parity between the sample members in the basic research variables (chronological age, height, mass, and training age) and it was found that the sample is homogeneous and equal.

Means, tools and devices used in the research

Researchers have relied on several means, tools and devices to reach the results of the research as follows:

- 1- Means of gathering information
- 2- The researchers used the following to collect the information.
- 3- Arab and foreign sources
- 4- Tests and measurements

Tools and devices used in the research:

Flying balls –(15) a ring device fixed to a stand - a whistle - a metal tape measure - wooden boxes with a height of (80) cm³ - colored adhesive tapes - a device for measuring weight - a rope length of (9 m-).

Tests and benchmarks

Field defense skill tests

First: Test the skillful and tactical performance of defending the stadium against the Qatari and straight attack from two centers (2-4) (4:81).

The purpose of the test: To measure the accuracy of the skillful and tactical performance of the players in the skill of defending the field from a diagonal or straight attack in two centers (2-4), coming from a good or not good reception or defense.

The tools used: the volleyball court, 15 balls, a tape measure, a tape measure, a rope with a length of (9) m and a height of (1.80) m parallel to the offensive line (3 m).

Performance characteristics: The defensive players stand in the backcourt in the positions (1-5), and the preparer prepares from a position (3 or 6) on the opposite court to one of the forward offensive centers (2 and 4) from a ball coming from the coach, and the attackers standing on crates attack in a manner. Diagonal or straight, the direction is unknown, (attack on the entire back area) (diagonal or straight) as the testers move and take the defensive formation according to the type and direction of the attack.

- ✓ Conditions: Testers have (3) attempts to defend the field for each position without direction.
- ✓ Scoring: (3) scores are given for each defensive attempt who delivered the ball to center (3) above the level of the rope.
- ✓ A score of (2) is given for each defensive attempt who delivered the ball below the rope level in the front zone.
- ✓ A score of one is given for each attempt the ball is directed to the backcourt and within the boundaries of the court 0 for every failed defense attempt.
- ✓ The maximum score for the laboratory is (9) for each center.

Pre-tests

The researchers conducted pre-tests on the research sample on Thursday 5/10/2019 at three in the afternoon and on the playground of the Specialized School for Volleyball in the Abi Al-Khasib district in Basra Governorate, as tests were conducted for the skill of defending the stadium, as previously described in the topic.

Main experience:

The researchers applied the main research experiment on the experimental group, which lasted (8) weeks for the period from 6/10/2019 to 1/6/2020, where the researchers used two educational units per week, bringing the number of units (16) corrective teaching units.

Dimensional tests

In order to establish the scientific facts for the skill and planning tests, the researchers conducted the post tests of the research sample on Saturday 8/1/2020, at the same time for the tribal tests and on the playground of the Specialized School for Volleyball in the Abi Al Khasib district in the Basra Governorate.

Statistical methods: The researchers used the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.

Presentation and discussion of results:

Displaying the results of the skill tests and plans of the control group in the pre and post measurements of the skill of defending the stadium

Table (1) shows the arithmetic mean, the standard deviation, the standard error, and the (T) value calculated for the pre and posttest of the control group of the field defense skill against an offensive ball prepared for good or not good reception or defense

Error level	Calculated	Standard error T value	Post test		The pretest		the exams	No
			standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Arithmetic mean		
0.004	3.703	0.212	0,911	6,34	0,89	4,95	Defending the stadium against the Qatari attack from 4 center	1
0.003	3.973	0.260	0,60	6,77	0,10	5,112	Defending the stadium against the Qatari attack from the 2nd position	2
0.004	3.873	0.208	0,501	6,32	0,961	5,487	Defend the field against a 4 center straight attack	3
0.006	3.545	0.396	0.383	7,12	2,002	5,382	Defend the field against a 2 center straight attack	4

Displaying the results of the skill tests and plans of the experimental group in the pre and post measurements of the skill of defending the stadium.

Table (2) shows the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, standard error, and (T) value calculated for the pre and posttest of the experimental group of the field defense skill against an attack ball prepared for good or not good reception or defense

Error level	Calculated	Standard error T value	Post test		The pretest		the exams	No
			standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Arithmetic mean		
0.001	5.237	0.302	0.843	7,64	2.08	6,08	Defending the stadium against the Qatari attack from 4 center	1
0.003	4.000	0.410	0.923	6,800	3,302	5,819	Defending the stadium against the Qatari attack from the 2nd position	2
0.001	5.237	0.30	0.816	8,56	2,05	6,01	Defend the field against a 4 center straight attack	3
0.000	7.799	0,459	0.478	8.80	5,0	5,03	Defend the field against a 2 center straight attack	4

Discussing the results of the skill and planning tests of the two groups of research in the pre and post measures of the skill of defending the stadium.

The two previous tables show that there are significant statistical differences in favor of the experimental group, and the researchers attribute this to the use of the educational curriculum by the trainer based on good scientific foundations, which included innovative educational exercises for the defensive planning performance of the research sample, which was prepared and implemented depending on the learning methods the appropriate

response and accompanying the implementation of the curriculum (feedback) in order to modify the performance and adjust it in proportion to the level of the sample for the purpose of correcting previous errors, which in turn was reflected in the level of the planned skill performance, and this is what was indicated by (Yarb Khayun, 2002). External feedback accelerates the rate of skill learning, and the corrective exercises that were prepared by the researchers included the two characteristics of kinetic expectation and reaction speed of the offensive ball, as these exercises contributed to the development of the skill and tactical performance of the players of the experimental group in the skill of defending the field, as (Talha Husam al-Din, 1997) affirms (The volleyball player must live the state of expectation in all his joints and in all moments of skillful performance. The correct expectation in estimating the requirements of each skill against the various offensive skills) (1: 117), and the regularity of the players in the educational curriculum prepared by the coach helped the development of the planned performance, and this is confirmed by (Magil.2004), "It is one of the natural aspects of the learning process. There must be an improvement in learning as long as the trainer follows the correct steps and foundations of the learning process and practicing the correct performance and focusing on it until the performance is established and steadfast. "(273: 9). The trainer and the educational methods used provide learners with essential external feedback for the purpose of improving the level of skill performance. (95: 9), (also one of the benefits of planned skill-performance exercises is the approach to playing situations that make learners with these exercises know about a variety of situations as a result of applying the exercises, which makes all learners interactive in the performance of skills and effectively, as well as providing learners cognitively and physically. On the environment of playing and competition and teaching them to alter performance to suit the playing environment, its variables and its processes (8: 89), and since training on planned performance that is highly similar to competitions has greatly increased the confidence component of the sample players. Experimentalism and thus reflected on the development of skillful performance, and confirms (Medhat Saleh, 2018), "One of the important features in the sports field is the increase in self-confidence of the players that results from training in a modern and advanced way, because it contributes to (positive emotions, positive self-awareness, Flexibility and ease of adaptation to others, focus, and reduce performance anxiety, in addition to successful performance) "(408: 3), and the researchers are specialized in volleyball training, knowing the importance of innovative defensive exercises that were formulated in the educational curriculum and its suitability for the players, the required time and the number of repetitions. For exercises, make the goals that have been scientifically set that have effectively contributed to the development of the planning performance of the skill of defending the stadium among the experimental research sample, and this is consistent with what was indicated by (Qasim Hassan Hussein 1998) "The educational process is that continuous organized process that gains the individual Knowledge, skill, ability, ideas and opinions needed to perform a specific job or achieve a specific goal, as well as a method for achieving organizational goals and adapting to work and what provides the individual with specific information, skills, or mental attitudes needed. (178: 2).

The reactivity of the exercises prepared by the researchers, which married the skillful aspect and the planning requirement of each exercise, showed the learner his planned role on the field and the importance of his taking his correct position and his relationship to his responsibilities towards the players next to him and his movements according to each formation of the blocking wall for the team (117: 5). And after the emergence of statistically significant differences in the post-tests between the two groups and in favor of the experimental group, the assumption of the research was achieved with the presence of statistically significant differences.

Conclusions and recommendations

Conclusions

- 1- The exercises used contributed to the development of planned skill performance significantly among the experimental research sample.
- 2- Mastering the skill of defending the stadium in its various forms gave positive results in the development of defensive formations according to the type of attack.
- 3- The youngsters' learning according to modern exercises that are far from the stereotypes and similar to playing situations were in itself a reinforcing motive in learning and mastering the planned skill performance.

Recommendations

- 1- A real interest in developing the technical forms of defending the stadium because of their real impact on the game.
- 2- The development of defensive forms requires modernity, suspense and excitement, in contrast to the offensive skills that are originally a catalyst to arouse the motivations of the learners.
- 3- Emphasis on integrating the planned performance early because of its positive results in developing the level of players in the later stages.

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Author Information

Asst. Prof. Dr. Wathiq Abdulsahib Oubed

College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences,
Al Basrah University, Iraq

Asst. Prof. Dr. Raja Abdulsamad Ashoor

College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences,
Al Basrah University, Iraq

Asst. Prof. Dr. Shehab Ghalib Shehab

College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences,
Al Basrah University, Iraq
